

ENHANCEMENT OF TEACHER EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE UTILIZATION OF CHATGPT: A QUALITATIVE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

To collect data on the participants' perspectives and experiences, a qualitative phenomenological research design in the form of in-depth interviews was used. Phenomenological research, according to Bliss (2016), is a qualitative research technique that tries to comprehend and characterize the universal core of a phenomena by analyzing lived experiences in order to get deeper insights into how individuals perceive such experiences. The following are the major findings: ChatGPT improves teaching techniques, efficiency, and learning experience. While it simplifies activities and content development, ethical considerations highlight the importance of responsible integration, and success is dependent on resolving contextual variables and instructor competency. It is possible to infer that ChatGPT is a context-dependent technology that provides essential assistance to instructors attempting to strike a compromise between efficiency and tailored education.

Keywords: *Teacher Efficiency, Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a dynamic field, constantly evolving to meet the needs of learners in an increasingly complex world. Teachers, at the heart of this transformation, play a critical role in shaping the educational experiences of students (Wentzel, 2015). There are many qualities that a teacher must possess in order to perform as highly as possible and one of these is efficiency.

According to Gager (2018), efficiency is the often measurable ability to avoid wasting materials, energy, efforts, money, and time while performing a task. In a more general sense, it

is the ability to do things well, successfully, and without waste. When teaching and efficiency comes hand in hand, it stands as a linchpin in the realm of education. Teacher efficiency is a factor that significantly impacts the quality of learning, the academic achievement of students, and the overall educational experience.

However, educators often find themselves grappling with a multitude of challenges that can hinder their efficiency including managing diverse student needs, developing engaging instructional materials, and staying updated with the latest educational research. In this fast-paced world, where information is constantly evolving, educators need efficient tools to support their teaching efforts. In light of this, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising solution to address these challenges and enhance teacher efficiency (Bradzil & Jorge, 2021).

One such AI-powered tool that has gained attention in recent years is ChatGPT. The Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (ChatGPT or ChatGPT Playground) is an artificial intelligence (AI) tool developed by OpenAI that allows for the generation of text based on user prompts. It has been specifically designed to comprehend natural language and produce intelligent and pertinent responses to user inquiries (Halaweh, 2023). The technology of ChatGPT has the potential to revolutionize the field of education by assisting teachers in various aspects of their work. A research suggested by Atlas (2023) states that ChatGPT can provide immediate answers to student queries, offering personalized assistance, clarifications, and additional explanations. It can act as a virtual tutor, extending learning support beyond the classroom.

Baidoo-Anu & Owusu Ansah (2023) articulates that ChatGPT can assist in curriculum development by generating relevant content, suggesting teaching strategies, and aiding in lesson planning. It can help educators create engaging and up-to-date materials. In addition, according to Dwivedi et.al (2023), automating grading tasks can also be done with ChatGPT. It can save teachers substantial time and reduce grading bias. It can also offer students instant feedback, fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

Moreover, ChatGPT acts as a repository of educational knowledge. It can recommend research articles, best practices, and online courses, supporting teachers in their ongoing professional development (Bridgeman & Shipman, 2022). Lastly, Neuman (2022) asserts that ChatGPT can assist with administrative tasks such as scheduling, administrative inquiries, and communication with parents, allowing teachers to allocate more time to instruction.

However, while ChatGPT and similar AI models can offer numerous benefits in various educational contexts, there can also be negative impacts on teachers and disruptions from the real goal of efficiency in education. According to Haleem et.al (2022), building strong teacher-student relationships is essential for effective education. Overreliance on AI could lead to a reduction in the personal touch and mentorship that teachers provide, potentially impacting students' emotional and social development. Mucharras et.al (2023) suggests that AI models like ChatGPT have limitations in adapting to the diverse needs and learning styles of individual students. Teachers are skilled at tailoring their instruction to meet the unique needs of each student, and an overreliance on AI may neglect this aspect of education.

Excessive reliance on AI technology may also result in students and teachers becoming overly dependent on it. If there are technical issues or disruptions, it can disrupt the learning process and create frustration (Tlili e.at., 2023). Furthermore, teachers may need additional

training to effectively integrate AI into their teaching methods. The rapid advancement of technology can create skill gaps, making it challenging for some educators to keep up with the latest developments (De Castro, 2023).

To add, according to Morron (2023), AI models like ChatGPT may provide standardized and formulaic responses, potentially discouraging creativity in both teaching and learning. It could be worrisome if teachers and students will prioritize AI-generated content over creative thinking. Ultimately, a shift toward automated grading and support systems can reduce the sense of professional satisfaction that teachers derive from their work. Many educators find fulfillment in the personalized interactions and intellectual challenges of teaching, which AI may not fully replicate (Seo et.al, 2021).

The utilization of ChatGPT in education has the potential to revolutionize the teaching and learning process. As education continues to evolve in response to the demands of the digital age, AI tools like ChatGPT can empower teachers, streamline their workflows, and foster more effective and learning environments. However, ethical considerations and potential challenges must be addressed responsibly to ensure equitable and effective integration.

In line with the narratives stated above, the purpose of this study was to explore the possibility and capabilities of the utilization of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency. The result of the study aimed to contribute valuable insights into the practical implications of utilizing ChatGPT in education, shedding light on its potential to enhance teacher efficiency and improve the overall educational experience for both teachers and students. Ultimately, it sought to offer insights into the responsible implementation of ChatGPT in the educational field.

Research Questions

1. How do teachers perceive the role of ChatGPT in supporting their teaching practices and enhancing their efficiency in the classroom?
2. What specific tasks and responsibilities do teachers believe ChatGPT can assist them with in their daily work, and how does this affect their workload?
3. What ethical considerations do teachers have regarding the use of ChatGPT in education, including concerns related to data privacy, bias, and potential implications for their role as educators?
4. What are the contextual factors and challenges that influence the successful integration of ChatGPT into teachers' daily routines, and how do these factors impact teacher efficiency?
5. How do teachers perceive the overall effectiveness of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study on determining the impact the utilization of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency employed a qualitative research approach in the form of in-depth interviews to gather data on the perceptions and experiences of the participants. Specifically, the study relied on a qualitative phenomenological research design. According to Bliss (2016), phenomenological research is a qualitative research approach that seeks to understand and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon by studying lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences. Furthermore, the design aimed to interpret the participants' feelings, perceptions, and beliefs to clarify the essence of the phenomenon under investigation. A qualitative phenomenological research design is the most appropriate approach for this study as it intended to understand and interpret the teacher experiences and perceptions regarding ChatGPT in order to unravel its underlying impacts in terms to promoting teacher efficiency.

Research Respondents

The study utilized a purposive sampling to select a sample of eight (8) key informants. Purposive sampling is a widely recognized qualitative research technique that involves the deliberate selection of a sample that best suits the study's objectives based on the researchers' expertise. This method seeks to amass comprehensive knowledge about a particular population or phenomenon of interest (Siripipatthanakul et al., 2022). Moreover, to be eligible for participation in the study, the individuals had to satisfy two inclusion criteria, including being a licensed teacher and having recent knowledge and experience in using ChatGPT.

Research Instrument

This study utilized one of the instruments in qualitative research which is the primary instrument who is the researcher himself. According to Friese (2010), in qualitative studies, the human investigator is the primary instruments for the gathering and analyzing of data. The study used face-to-face individual interview in gathering data. Ary (2010) states that interviews are used in gathering data from people about opinions, beliefs, and feelings about situations in their own words. Specifically, the study made use of semi-structured interview wherein a series of questions and issues to be discussed will be prepared before the discussion. Semi-structured interview gives the researchers an opportunity to clarify pertinent issues and questions that occurred during the interviewing process. It also allows the researcher to read the non-verbal communication and reactions which is necessary for the data analysis (Ferreira et al., 1988). In addition, the researcher recorded the interview using a voice recorder from a mobile phone.

Data Analysis

This study utilized Thematic analysis, a method of analyzing qualitative data that is usually applied to a set of texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researcher closely examined the data to identify common themes—topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly, as recommended by Namraksa and Kraiwanit (2023).

RESULTS

The responses of the participants in each research question were examined using thematic analysis, wherein the answers are grouped in topics and coded based on how many synonyms there are in each response.

Table 1. Role of ChatGPT in supporting teaching practices and enhancing efficiency in the classroom

Themes	Codes
Classroom Assistant	Serve as a valuable assistant in the classroom as is serves as a knowledge resource and assist with student inquiries (2) Functions as a supportive tool for teachers especially in lesson planning, providing them with quick access to information and resources (1)
Time-Saving Tool	Ability to provide quick answers to common questions, allowing them to redirect their focus towards interactive teaching and student engagement (2)
Personalized Learning Support	Caters to individual student needs by offering explanations and resources tailored to each student which enhances the learning experience and acknowledges the diverse learning styles and needs of students (1)
Accessibility Enhancement	Helps bridge language and learning style gaps making education more inclusive and ensuring that all students, regardless of their backgrounds or abilities, can access the curriculum (1)
Burden Reduction	Reduces administrative burdens by assisting with grading, assignment feedback, and administrative tasks, enabling educators to devote more time to teaching and mentoring students (1)

The participants' replies to the first research question about their perception on the role of ChatGPT in supporting their teaching practices and enhancing their efficiency in the classroom are shown in Table 1.

Table 2. Specific tasks and responsibilities ChatGPT can assist in teacher’s daily work and how does it affect workload

Themes	Codes
Routine Task Efficiency	Significantly contributes to efficiency by handling routine tasks, specifically providing explanations, generating content, offering instant feedback to students, and automating grading and assessment (2)
Enhanced Grading and Assessment	Ability to automate certain aspects in grading and assessment, making it more efficient allowing educators to provide quicker and more constructive feedback, emphasizing its positive impact on assessment-related tasks (2)
Streamlined Lesson Planning	Contributes to organized and effective lesson preparation while ensuring access to up-to-date resources (1)
Content Generation and Classroom Enrichment	Eases the burden of content generation for teachers and contributes to more interactive classroom interactions, benefiting teachers educators and students (1)
24/7 Learning Support	Enhances students' learning experiences while reducing the need for extensive after-hours support for teachers, ultimately enhancing work-life balance (2)

The participants’ replies to the second research question about the specific tasks and responsibilities ChatGPT can assist them in their daily work and how does it affect their workload are shown in Table 2.

Table 3. Ethical considerations regarding the use of ChatGPT in education including concerns related to data privacy, bias, and potential implications for teacher’s role as educators

Themes	Codes
Data Privacy Concerns	Teachers worry about how interactions with ChatGPT are logged and used, as well as the potential mishandling of sensitive information underscoring the importance of safeguarding data and privacy while using AI tools in education (3)
Bias and Fairness	Teachers emphasize the need for ChatGPT to provide fair and unbiased information, and they

	express concerns about the tool inadvertently perpetuating stereotypes or misinformation (1)
Impact on Critical Thinking	Teachers are mindful of the impact of ChatGPT on students' critical thinking skills. They want to strike a balance between AI assistance and nurturing students' ability to think independently and critically (1)
Role of Teachers as Guides and Mentors	Teachers express concerns that over-reliance on ChatGPT might diminish their role as guides and mentors. They worry that this reliance could reduce the human touch and emotional support they offer to students (2)
Responsible AI Use in Education	Teachers recognize the importance of teaching students responsible AI use. They want to ensure that students understand the limits and potential pitfalls of relying solely on AI for learning and problem-solving (1)

The participants' replies to the third research question about the ethical considerations regarding the use of ChatGPT in education are shown in Table 3.

Table 4. Contextual factors and challenges that influence the successful integration of ChatGPT into teachers' daily routines, and how do these factors impact teacher efficiency

Themes	Codes
Technology and Internet Access	Teachers note that the availability of technology and internet access plays a crucial role in their ability to integrate ChatGPT effectively. Those in areas with limited access may face challenges, underlining the importance of infrastructure in AI integration (2)
Teacher Proficiency with AI tools	Teachers who are more tech-savvy find it easier to incorporate ChatGPT into their lessons. However, it is acknowledged that some educators may require additional training to harness the tool's full potential, highlighting the importance of professional development (2)
Curriculum Adaptability	Teachers recognize that some subjects and teaching methods may be more amenable to ChatGPT, while others may require creative adjustments for effective integration (1)

Resistance to Change	Teachers, students, and administrators may resist adapting to new ways of teaching with ChatGPT. Overcoming this resistance is critical for the successful integration of AI tools in education (2)
Contextual Factors	Contextual factors such as class size and diversity are identified as playing a role. Larger classes or highly diverse student populations may have distinct needs and challenges when it comes to integrating ChatGPT (1)

The participants' replies to the fourth research question about the contextual factors and challenges that influence the successful integration of ChatGPT into teacher's daily routines and how do these factors impact teacher efficiency re shown in Table 4.

Table 5. Perceptions on the overall effectiveness of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency

Themes	Codes
Enhancement of Teacher Efficiency	The statements emphasize that teachers perceive ChatGPT as highly effective in enhancing their efficiency. It reduces the time spent on routine tasks, allowing educators to allocate more time to interactive and engaging aspects of teaching.
Dependency on Teacher's Ability	The effectiveness of ChatGPT is not solely based on the tool itself but is directly proportional to the teacher's ability to leverage its capabilities. Educators who effectively integrate it into their teaching routines are the ones who benefit the most.
Context-Dependent Effectiveness	While ChatGPT is considered a powerful tool, its effectiveness may vary depending on the subject and specific classroom needs. It is recognized as a supportive tool, rather than a replacement for traditional teaching methods, highlighting the importance of context in its use.
Positive Impact on Student Learning	Teachers acknowledge that ChatGPT's effectiveness extends beyond efficiency gains. It positively impacts student learning outcomes by providing personalized support and resources, indicating its potential to enhance the overall quality of education.

Valuable Addition to Educator's Toolkit	The general consensus is that ChatGPT is a valuable addition to the modern educator's toolkit. It provides benefits in terms of time savings, accessibility, and personalized support, ultimately enhancing overall teacher efficiency. This suggests that it is well-received as a complementary tool in education.
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The participants' replies to the fifth research question about their perception to the overall effectiveness of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency are shown in Table 5.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study have provided insights about the perceptions of teachers regarding the enhancement of teacher efficiency through the utilization of ChatGPT. The following are the discussion of the responses in each research question relative to the study:

I. Role of ChatGPT in supporting teaching practices and enhancing efficiency in the classroom

The thematic analysis for research question 1 reveals that teachers perceive ChatGPT as a multifaceted tool that plays a critical role in education. It acts as a knowledge resource, time-saving tool, and personalized learning aid while enhancing accessibility and reducing administrative burdens, ultimately improving teaching efficiency and the quality of the learning experience for students.

II. Specific tasks and responsibilities ChatGPT can assist in teacher's daily work and how does it affect workload

The thematic analysis for research question 2 reveals that ChatGPT offers substantial support in various aspects of teaching, ranging from routine tasks and grading to lesson planning, content generation, and 24/7 learning support. The tool's contributions to efficiency and workload reduction are central to these themes, highlighting its potential to streamline teaching responsibilities and improve the overall teaching experience.

III. Ethical considerations regarding the use of ChatGPT in education including concerns related to data privacy, bias, and potential implications for teacher's role as educators

The thematic analysis for research question 3 reveals that teachers have legitimate ethical concerns about the use of ChatGPT in education. These concerns encompass data privacy, bias, the impact on critical thinking skills, the role of teachers as mentors, and the importance of educating students about responsible AI use. These themes underscore the need for responsible and thoughtful integration of AI tools in educational settings, with a focus on ensuring student well-being and ethical use of technology.

IV. Contextual factors and challenges that influence the successful integration of ChatGPT into teachers' daily routines, and how do these factors impact teacher efficiency

The thematic analysis for research question 4 reveals that successful integration of ChatGPT into teachers' daily routines is influenced by several factors, including technology access, teacher proficiency, curriculum adaptability, resistance to change, and contextual factors. Addressing these factors is essential to ensure the effective use of AI tools in education and to tailor their implementation to the unique needs of each classroom.

V. Perceptions on the overall effectiveness of ChatGPT in enhancing teacher efficiency

The thematic analysis for research question 5 highlights the multifaceted role of ChatGPT in education. While it can significantly enhance teacher efficiency and positively impact student learning, its effectiveness is context-dependent and relies on the teacher's ability to effectively integrate it into their teaching methods. Overall, it is seen as a valuable addition to the modern educator's toolkit, offering a balance between efficiency and personalized support.

Conclusions

The research findings shed light on the multifaceted role of ChatGPT in the field of education. Thematic analysis of responses to five distinct research questions revealed a nuanced perspective among teachers regarding the impact of ChatGPT on their teaching practices and overall efficiency. ChatGPT has a diverse function in education, serving as a great resource for instructors to increase their efficiency and the quality of students' learning experiences. It aids in many parts of education, from everyday duties to content creation, but ethical concerns, such as data privacy and prejudice, underline the importance of appropriate integration. The effective implementation of ChatGPT is dependent on resolving contextual issues like as technology access and instructor competency. While it has the potential to dramatically improve teacher efficiency, its overall success is context-dependent and is contingent on instructors' ability to properly incorporate it into their teaching approaches. As a result, ChatGPT is a vital addition to the modern educator's arsenal, providing a mix of efficiency and individualized help in instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. It is crucial to provide teachers with training and professional development opportunities to enhance their proficiency in using ChatGPT effectively. This should include both technical training and guidance on ethical considerations in AI use.
2. Develop and communicate clear ethical guidelines for the use of ChatGPT in education. These guidelines should address issues such as data privacy, bias mitigation, and the role of teachers in shaping responsible AI use.
3. Acknowledge the contextual factors that influence the successful integration of ChatGPT. These may include technology access, curriculum adaptability, and resistance to change. Tailor support and resources to address these factors on a case-by-case basis.

4. Continuously evaluate the impact of ChatGPT on teacher efficiency and student learning outcomes. This research should consider the context in which it is used and adapt accordingly.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The quality and integrity of the research was considered by following several ethical standards: First, the researcher sought consent from the respondents to inform them about all the information about the study they need to decide whether they want to participate. Second, the researcher ensured that the participants will only participate voluntarily and will have the freedom to withdraw at any time. Third, the researcher made sure to maintain the anonymity of the respondents and not disclose their personal information to anyone. In addition, the researcher ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the gathered data from the respondents. Fourth, the researchers made sure to minimize the risk and maximize the benefits of the study for the participants. Fifth, the researcher respected the values and the interest of the participants as a whole and protected them from any harm. Sixth, the researcher guaranteed there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research. Seventh and last, the researcher made sure that any acts of plagiarism in writing and conducting the research were avoided.

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REFERENCES

- Alshammari, R., McGuire, R., & Myers, J. (2020). Investigating the Impact of Digital Learning Technologies on Student Engagement in Higher Education. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 28(8), 1078-1091. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1704363>.
- Atlas, S. (2023). ChatGPT for Higher Education and Professional Development: A Guide to Conversational AI. University of Rhode Island. https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/cba_facpubs/548.
- Baidoo-Anu, D., & Owusu Ansah, L. (2023). Education in the era of generative artificial intelligence (AI): Understanding the potential benefits of ChatGPT in promoting teaching and learning. Available at SSRN 4337484. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4337484>.
- BLISS, L. 2016. Phenomenological Research: Inquiry to Understand the Meaning of People's Experiences. *International Journal of Adult Vocational Education and Technology*.
- Brazdil, P.; Jorge, A. *Progress in Artificial Intelligence: Knowledge Extraction, Multi-Agent Systems, Logic Programming, and Constraint Solving*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2021.
- Bridgeman, A. J., & Shipman, M. A. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and Education: Promises and Perils. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 3-22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0047239520984205>.
- Cotton, D. R., Cotton, P. A., & Shipway, J. R. (2023). Chatting and Cheating: Ensuring Academic Integrity in the Era of ChatGPT. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2190148>.
- De Castro, C.A. (2023). A Discussion about the Impact of ChatGPT in Education: Benefits and Concerns. *Journal of Business Theory and Practice*. doi:10.22158/jbtp.v11n2p28
- Dwivedi, Y.K., Kshetri, N., Hughes, L., Slade, E.L., Jeyaraj, A., Kar, A.K., Baabdullah, A.M., Koohang, A., Raghavan, V., Ahuja, M. and Albanna, H. (2023). "So What If ChatGPT Wrote It?" Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Opportunities, Challenges and Implications of Generative Conversational AI for Research, Practice and Policy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 71, 102642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2023.102642>.
- Friese, S. 2010. Data collection - Which steps to follow? <https://atlasti.com/research-hub/data-collection>. Accessed on January 11, 2023.
- Gager, A. (2018). Efficiency and Effectiveness: Know the Difference. Retrieved from <https://www.facilitiesnet.com/maintenanceoperations/article/Efficiency-and-Effectiveness-Know-the-Difference--17835>
- Halaweh, M. (2023). ChatGPT in education: Strategies for responsible implementation. *Contemp. Educ. Technol.* 15, 421
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275-285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.05.004>
- King, M. R., & ChatGPT. (2023). A Conversation on Artificial Intelligence, Chatbots, and Plagiarism in Higher Education. *Cellular and Molecular Bioengineering*, 16(1), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12195-022-00754-8>.
- Limna, P., Jakwatanatham, S., Siripipattanakul, S., Kaewpuang, P., & Sriboonruang, P. (2022). A Review of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education During the Digital Era. *Advance Knowledge for Executives*, 1(1), 1-9. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4160798>.
- Morrison, M. (2023). The Impact of AI on Learning and Creativity: A Critical Look at the Future. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impact-ai-learning-creativity-critical-look-future-miriam-morrison>

- Mucharraz y Cano, Y., Francesco Venuti, F., & Herrera Martinez, R. (2023, fevereiro 1). ChatGPT and AI Text Generators: Should Academia Adapt or Resist? Harvard Business School Publishing.
- Namraksa, S., & Kraiwanit, T. (2023). Parental Expectations for International Schools in The Digital Age. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(1), 1-7. <https://www.ujer.org/vol2no1/article121>.
- Neuman, M.; Rauschenberger, M.; Schön, E.M. "We Need To Talk About ChatGPT": The Future of AI and Higher Education. *Hochschule Hannover 2022*, 1, 1–4.
- Seo, K., Tang, J., Roll, I. et al. The impact of artificial intelligence on learner–instructor interaction in online learning. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 18, 54 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00292-9>
- Siripipatthanakul, S., Muthmainnah, Siripipattanakul, S., Sriboonruang, P., Kaewpuang, P., Sitthipon, T., Limna, P., & Jaipong, P. (2023b). Gamification and Edutainment in 21st Century Learning. In Taslim, et.al (Ed.), *Multidisciplinary Approaches to Research* (Vol. 2, pp. 210-219). Indonesia: Yayasan Corolla Education Centre. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4367648>.
- Sok, S., & Heng, K. (2023). ChatGPT for Education and Research: A Review of Benefits and Risks. Available at SSRN 4378735. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4378735>.
- Tlili, A., Shehata, B., Adarkwah, M. A., Bozkurt, A., Hickey, D. T., Huang, R., & Agyemang, B. (2023). What if the devil is my guardian angel: ChatGPT as a case study of using chatbots in education. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00237-x>
- Wentzel, K. R. (2015). Teacher-student relationships and adolescent competence at school. In *Handbook of competence and motivation* (pp. 405-421). Guilford Press.